

УДК 372.881.111.1

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14066511

Научная статья

МЕСТО И РОЛЬ КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ ИНОЯЗЫЧНЫХ ГРАММАТИЧЕСКИХ НАВЫКОВ НА СРЕДНЕМ ЭТАПЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE GRAMMATICAL SKILLS AT THE MIDDLE STAGE OF EDUCATION

ЛИНЕВА ЕЛЕНА АЛЕКСАНДРОВНА,

кандидат филологических наук, доцент,

ГОУ МО ВО «Государственный гуманитарно-технологический университет».

ОВЧИННИКОВА МАРИЯ ВИКТОРОВНА,

кандидат педагогических наук, доцент,

ГОУ МО ВО «Государственный гуманитарно-технологический университет».

САХАРОВА АННА ВЛАДИМИРОВНА,

кандидат философских наук, доцент,

ГОУ МО ВО «Государственный гуманитарно-технологический университет».

ГРУШИНА МАРГАРИТА ВЛАДИМИРОВНА,

кандидат филологических наук, доцент,

ГОУ МО ВО «Государственный гуманитарно-технологический университет».

LINEVA ELENA ALEXANDROVNA,

PhD in Philology, Associate Professor,

State University of Humanities and Technology.

OVCHINNIKOVA MARIA VICTOROVNA,

PhD in Pedagogy, Associate Professor,

State University of Humanities and Technology.

SAKHAROVA ANNA VLADIMIROVNA,

PhD in Philology, Associate Professor,

State University of Humanities and Technology.

GRUSHINA MARGARITA VLADIMIROVNA,

PhD in Philology, Associate Professor,

State University of Humanities and Technology.

В данной статье рассматривается процесс развития грамматических навыков английского языка. Изучается вопрос использования современных компьютерных технологий при обучении грамматике английского языка обучающихся средней школы. Проводится анализ педагогической и методической литературы и нормативных документов. Приводятся существующие информационно-коммуникационные технологии для обучения грамматике английского языка на среднем этапе. Сделан вывод, что на сегодняшний день учитель обладает неограниченным количеством дополнительных источников передачи знаний об изучаемом грамматическом явлении, что является весомым преимуществом средств ИКТ над другими формами наглядности.

This article discusses the process of developing grammatical skills of the English language. The issue of using modern computer technologies in teaching English grammar to secondary school students is being studied. The analysis of pedagogical and methodological literature and normative documents is carried out. The existing information and communication technologies for teaching English grammar at the middle stage are presented. It is concluded that today the teacher has an unlimited number of additional sources of knowledge transfer about the grammatical phenomenon being studied, which is a significant advantage of ICT tools over other forms of visibility.

Ключевые слова: компьютерные технологии, грамматический навык, речевая деятельность, метод, форма, средство.

Key words: computer technology, grammar skill, speech activity, method, form, means.

Grammar acts as a key component contributing to the formation of foreign language communicative competence and the development of skills in four types of speech activity (speaking, reading, listening and writing), which in turn is one of the most difficult and at the same time one of the most important aspects of teaching a foreign language.

Teaching the grammatical side of speech in secondary school is based on the study of a large number of grammatical rules. In this regard, there is a problem of misunderstanding by many students of the stated principles of formation of certain grammatical structures, due to the presence of complex terminology in the rules, which further contributes to the appearance of errors in oral and written speech. Therefore, for the successful formation and development of grammar skills in secondary school students, the teacher must choose the right approach to the process of teaching the grammatical side of speech, key methods, forms and means of teaching.

In recent years, the role of using modern computer technologies in organizing lessons has increased, the purpose of which is to study, systematize and consolidate knowledge about the grammatical structure of a foreign language. The use of innovative information and communication technologies allows the teacher to involve students in the educational process, increase their interest and motivation to the studied grammatical material, with their help, timely control of knowledge, skills and abilities takes place.

It should be noted that modern information and communication technologies make it possible to implement a system-activity approach to learning, which is the basis of the second-generation FGOS. This approach, in turn, is aimed at forming the readiness of secondary school students to independently search for knowledge in such educational conditions that are focused on their individual, age and psychological characteristics. Innovative computer technologies contribute to the creation of the above-described educational conditions due to the wide range of their pedagogical capabilities.

Based on the above, the chosen topic for research is relevant, since with the help of the latest information and communication technologies, the process of teaching the grammatical side of speech becomes fascinating and interesting due to the possibility of choosing various methods, forms and means of teaching. In addition, modern computer technologies are characterized by a high communicative orientation, which in turn meets the requirements prescribed in the educational standard of the second generation.

The theoretical basis of this research work is the works of such domestic researchers in the field of linguistics and methodology as I.L. Bim, V.G. Gak, N.D. Galskova, M.N. Evstigneeva, V.P. Leontiev, E.N. Solovova, E.V. Pobortseva, G.V. Rogovoy. The works of these authors raise the issues of teaching the grammatical side of speech at the middle stage using modern computer technologies.

The use of information and communication technologies in English lessons in the development of grammar skills in middle grades is more effective, since children of this age assimilate in-

formation with the help of visual materials much better. In particular, visualization using ICT allows the teacher to present a huge number of complex rules studied in the section "English Grammar" in the most accessible and concise way.

In order to understand exactly what information and communication technologies exist and how they can be used in teaching English grammar at the middle stage, consider the following classification presented by Professor N.D. Galskova in her article "Typology of e-learning technologies for foreign languages".

Information and communication technologies, depending on their main purpose, are divided into the following three groups:

- Demonstration technologies.
- Technologies based on network resources-the Internet.
- Multimedia technologies [1, pp. 37-41; 4].

Galskova considers presentations and an interactive whiteboard to be among the demonstration technologies. That is, these are technologies used to provide information.

The use of presentations is the most accessible way to assimilate and consolidate the grammatical material studied in the middle classes.

When teaching grammar, two types of presentations are used – static and interactive. The first one assumes more clarity and is suitable for the introduction and primary consolidation of grammatical material. Interactive views involve both studying the information presented on the slides and changing the content of the slides themselves.

The use of presentations to enhance cognitive activity can occur at various stages and types of classes. For example, when introducing new grammatical material in middle classes, electronic accompaniment in the form of a presentation can be created, which will reflect the basic concepts, an algorithm for applying a grammatical rule, a video clip with authentic material demonstrating a particular grammatical phenomenon, or material for observation and comparisons can be offered [2, p. 173; 5].

N.D. Galskova's second group includes technologies based on the use of the Internet, which today can be considered as analog or alternative means in relation to traditional printed textbooks and teaching aids.

Since today the Internet covers all spheres of activity, its use for educational purposes is an integral part of the educational process.

Automated reference books and textbooks on English grammar for secondary school students are available on the Internet, which include information on the morphology and syntax of the English language.

With the help of the Internet, the development of grammar skills in secondary school is most successful, since today there are a huge number of online tests that allow you to track the level of proficiency in a foreign language, and in particular help to track how well children assimilate the grammatical material taught to them.

Finally, the third group, according to Professor N.D. Galskova, includes computer tools that simultaneously use sound, animated computer graphics and video sequences to present information in various forms (text, audio, graphic, video information) and provide a person with the opportunity to interact with it.

For example, the use of authentic songs presented on the Internet is a way to firmly assimilate grammatical material in English lessons in high school. The grammatical phenomena of language are better activated and assimilated in songs, since music is considered one of the most effective ways of memorizing material [3, p. 167; 6].

The use of ICT in teaching a foreign language significantly helps to improve various forms and methods of teaching, increases the interest of students in in-depth study of program material. The effectiveness of teaching the grammatical side of speech using a variety of information and

communication technologies is largely determined by the correct choice of their use. The element of novelty for students is the main criterion when learning a foreign language, because children are happy to receive knowledge presented in an unconventional, new form, and a properly selected type of ICT will allow them to conduct a lesson on the development of grammatical skills in the most exciting way.

Thus, there is currently a tendency to create conditions for the development of students' skills of independence and self-development through the use of new approaches. The most effective is the system-activity approach in teaching. Applicable to the subject of "Foreign language", the introduction of a system-activity approach allows for the general cultural and personal development of students. The system-activity approach in teaching grammar of a foreign language at the middle stage creates opportunities for active mastery of grammatical structures through the use of a variety of active forms, methods and technologies of teaching.

At the present stage of teaching a foreign language at school, a huge number of different technologies are used to develop grammatical skills, which make it possible to effectively organize the educational process. Information and communication technologies are among the most frequently used, since they include various types (demonstration technologies; technologies based on network resources-the Internet; multimedia technologies) that are actively used in the cognitive activity of students.

ICTs allow not only to diversify the learning process of the grammatical side of the speech of a foreign language, but also contribute to the comprehensive development of a secondary school student.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Гальскова Н.Д. Типология технологий электронного обучения иностранным языкам // Создание виртуального межкультурного образовательного пространства средствами технологий электронного обучения. 2017. С. 37-41.
2. Поборцева Е.В. Роль презентации при обучении грамматике иностранного языка // Академическая публицистика. 2021. № 2. С. 171-173.
3. Рогова Г.В., Верещагина И.Н. Методика обучения английскому языку на начальном этапе в средней школе. М.: Просвещение, 1988. 224 с.
4. Шобонова Л.Ю., Котылева Е.А., Белоусова Н.А. Средства электронного обучения в изучении иностранных языков // Мир науки. 2018. № 2. URL: <https://mir-nauki.com/PDF/89PDMN218>.
5. Лебедева Т.Е., Охотникова Н.В., Потапова Е.А. Электронная образовательная среда вуза: требования, возможности, опыт и перспективы использования // Мир науки. 2016. Т. 4. № 2. URL: <http://mir-nauki.com/PDF/57PDMN216>.
6. Леонтьева И.А., Ребрина Ф.Г. Применение дистанционных электронных учебных курсов в образовательном процессе высшей школы // Вестник Южно-Уральского государственного гуманитарно-педагогического университета. 2018. № 3. С. 114-124.

© Линева Е.А., Овчинникова М.В., Сахарова А.В., Грушина М.В., 2024.